

ACTOR NETWORK

DARIAH-FI

December 2022

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DARIAH-FI

ABOUT DARIAH-FI

DARIAH-FI is a new national research infrastructure created for the needs of data-intensive social sciences and humanities (SSH) in Finland. Currently, the best practices are scattered across individual research groups and universities. Our national network prevents overlapping work and encourages synergies inside the Finnish SSH community. In short, we build and share digital tools, datasets and workflows to facilitate high-quality SSH research.

Why DARIAH-FI?

Efficiency

Coordination on a national level helps to avoid duplication of work in individual research teams: more efficient use of limited resources in data-intensive SSH research.

Sustainability

Individual research teams do not have sufficient resources for long-term infrastructure building: our network builds sustainable solutions for data-intensive SSH research.

Funding

We facilitate the spread of digital competences in every Finnish university: increased chances for winning funding at the highest international level in data-intensive SSH research.

DARIAH-FI as part of FIN-CLARIAH

FIN-CLARIAH is a project funded by the Academy of Finland (2022-2023) that comprises two components, DARIAH-FI and FIN-CLARIN. In this context, FIN-CLARIN is a mature infrastructure with a high-quality service model through its online service centre The Language Bank of Finland.

The focus on centrally provided resources for language-based research of FIN-CLARIN will be complemented by the wider discipline base (e.g., history) and bottom-up approach to data and service creation of DARIAH-FI.

In addition to collaborating at the boundaries where their missions overlap, both DARIAH-FI and FIN-CLARIAH will share facilities for the management and negotiation of material rights, for technical access, as well as for hosting documentation, tools and services.

June 2015

Liber conference London, "Towards Open Science": Mikko Tolonen sat next to Mike Mertens (who had started as a director of DARIAH-EU) at the conference dinner. Agreed to investigate possibilities to work together with DARIAH-EU.

Autumn 2015

Faculty of Arts investments at UH on digital humanities scaled up (deans Arto Mustajoki and Hanna Snellman), collaboration with Eetu Mäkelä with respect to infrastructure development started.

April 2016

Mike Mertens visited University of Helsinki to discuss possibilities of collaboration with DARIAH-EU.

May 2016

Heldig (Helsinki Centre for Digital Humanities) founded; Eero Hyvönen director, Jouni Tuominen coordinating researcher.

2016-

Joining DARIAH-EU Working Groups.

2016-2017

DARIAH-FI survey of use of digital methods among early career humanities researchers in Finland (after DARIAH-EU surveys) by Inés Matres ([publication](#)).

October 2016

Keynote presentation at DARIAH-EU conference in Ghent, collaboration with Sally Chambers started.

2017-2019

Joined DESIR Humanities at Scale: Evolving the DARIAH-ERIC, Horizon2020 project led by Dariah-EU (our part: development of DARIAH in Finland) with Maija Paavolainen and Tuuli Tahko.

2017-

Collaborative Partner agreement between University of Helsinki DARIAH-EU (renewed in 2021); also Aalto made the same agreement.

October 2017

DARIAH-FI workshop for serious building of national consortium, Jennifer Edmond from DARIAH-EU joined us as keynote speaker.

2017-

DARIAH Nordic Hub development.

2018-

Building a consortium for DARIAH-FI application covering the Finnish Universities, CSC, National Library of Finland and National Archives.

2019

Academy of Finland Infrastructure application (made it to the final round, but not funded).

2020

Planning a roadmap together with large national partner pool and FIN-CLARIN as FIN-CLARIAH (supported by dean Pirjo Hiidenmaa; accepted to the Academy of Finland Infrastructure Roadmap).

2020

HSSH institute at University of Helsinki founded, Risto Kunelius director.

2021

Writing an application together with all the partners as FIN-CLARIAH for FIRI, director Krister Lindén (successful).

2022-

Putting the roadmap to practice and continue the process for joining DARIAH-EU.

DARIAH-FI

DARIAH-FI WORK PACKAGES

DARIAH-FI has eleven work packages (WPs) for the years 2022–2023. Each WP has a leader and one or more participants from the consortium partners or collaborators.

The WP leader and participants contribute to the work in the WP. Collaborators are test users providing feedback, evaluation and beta testing of the deliverables.

Noise-resistant NLP Models and Data

Veronika Laippala
WP leader

Natural language processing (NLP) tools can process standard language with extremely high performance, but the performance deteriorates when facing noisy, non-standard input. Noise can originate from non-standard language use and from the digitization process: (a) historical language varieties, dialects, spoken genres; (b) OCR noise, boilerplate remains from Web data, other non textual input. This WP develops datasets featuring noisy language and NLP tools that can survive noise.

Increasingly Automated Ingestion of Material

Development of a data ingestion pipeline where data providers such as cultural heritage institutions and companies can easily deposit their data for research use will be piloted. The foreseen impact is to make large materials digitized by cultural heritage institutions or donated by companies more rapidly available for research. This WP aims to deliver the copyright-free National Library of Finland material to the CSC Allas, for researcher use. This is either done via data dumps and/or by utilizing the digi.nationallibrary.fi OAI-PMH interface with some customization.

Johanna Lilja
WP leader

AI Solutions to Better Use National Archives Mass Digitisation Services

Jari Ojala
WP leader

The foreseen impact is to provide infrastructure to better use the mass digitisation service of the National Archives of Finland (NARC) in which the printed documents that are in the possession of State authorities and kept permanently or in long-term storage will be digitised. As the NARC have started the mass digitization in 2019, this WP aims at creating tools for analysis and annotation of the massive data produced in the process. The WP also aims to offer time-saving procedures for researchers who hope to use digitized data from the NARC.

AI Solutions to Better Use Textual Qualitative Survey Data

The lack of easy-to-use analysis tools for survey open text questions poses a challenge for researchers, especially in large datasets with thousands of respondents. Survey answers have rich structural and statistical contexts that sometimes extend to population representativeness. This WP aims to deliver a software package for the discovery of a network of related concepts from unstructured texts in Finnish, using a combination of AI and human input and a preliminary user interface for browsing and searching the results.

Krista Lagus
WP leader

Developing Analysis Methods for Real-time Chats in Game Play Streams

Raine Koskimaa

WP leader

One of the biggest transformations across contemporary media cultures is the proliferation of streamed audio-visual content with textual communication features. While online streams have been studied increasingly over the past years, the employed methods we currently have are typically qualitative or (if quantitative) lack the means for processing larger amounts of content. Thus, we need tools to study online streams quantitatively. The WP aims to offer machine learning tools to analyse interactions between audio-visual and textual communication.

Developing Analysis Methods for Text Network Analysis of Political Texts

Text network analysis (TNA) is a rather new approach in text mining, but has gained popularity when it comes to understanding thematic pathways and text recycling in unstructured document corpora by de- and re-constructing texts. Moreover, TNA as a flexible method is well-suited to tackle research questions and problems beyond text mining and topic modeling, as well as to process unstructured texts. The WP aims to offer an infrastructure to structure, store, and analyse large textual document corpora. The first data to be integrated consists of main political documents of the Finnish politics.

Kimmo Elo

WP leader

Metadata Harmonization and Analysis

Leo Lahti
WP leader

Digital metadata collections are valuable for cataloguing and information retrieval. They provide structured data that has a foreseen impact on developing methods, applications and tools, and they are increasingly recognized as a potential research object that allows large-scale statistical comparisons, albeit often only after substantial harmonization, enrichment, and curation. The WP aims to deliver a harmonized version of the Finnish National Bibliography (FNB) and a release of FNB and harmonization code as open data, an implementation of a data analysis and visualization workflow for FNB, and R/Python modules for bibliographic data analysis.

Linked Open Data Services

This WP focuses on maintaining and developing the Linked Open Data Infrastructure for Digital Humanities in Finland (LODI4DH) in collaboration with other partners within DARIAH-FI. Accordingly, the WP aims to develop and publish the underlying Linked Data Finland NLP knowledge extraction tools as web services for named entity linking, automatic keyword annotation, relation and event extraction, topic modelling, and semantic text classification. Also the underlying Parliament of Finland Ontology with its components will be published for re-use.

Eero Hyvönen
WP leader

Subsetting Data, Detecting Bias and Noise

Eetu Mäkelä

WP leader

The DARIAH-FI infrastructure gathers together datasets of interest to a wide community of researchers, but which have not originally been created for research. Such datasets contain biases, confounders and noise which need to be understood, evaluated and handled when using the data for research. The WP aims to deliver a process/service for indexing large datasets and robustly querying them for subsets of interest, an environment for obtaining statistical overviews of (sub)datasets to uncover and evaluate biases and suitability, and provide intelligent noise reduction applications for real-time social media data capture to identify bots and trolls.

Social Media Noise

Despite obvious benefits, high volume and velocity social big data are not yet widely used in SSH research for at least three reasons: (1) access to social media data requires some degree of technical competence; (2) social media data contain a lot of noise (e.g. material from software robots), which can seriously skew results; (3) for proprietary and ethical reasons, researchers have had limited access to social background information of account holders, which restricts theoretical insight based on social media in SSH. The WP aims to develop a unified process for making social media data available for researchers and to develop generic tools to enrich these data.

Mikko Laitinen

WP leader

Education, Dissemination and Evidence-Based Research Infrastructure Development

Sanna Kumpulainen
WP leader

Interaction refers to the necessity of collecting information on how researchers interact with the research infrastructure (RI) in order to develop the tools and services accordingly. It also refers to the need to offer education and consultation on how researchers can enhance their work by using the infrastructure, thus increasing the RI's active user base. Information Interaction (1) collects RI usage and performance data and (2) designs and develops methods, tools, protocols, services and learning environments to support RI analysis and development and to respond to the need for education and guidance on RI use.

DARIAH-FI

DARIAH-FI AND ITS ACTIVITIES

DARIAH-FI officially launched its activities on January 2022.

Since then, DARIAH-FI has: (1) organized two internal meetings with all the partners, (2) arranged four roadshows at different universities to present the research infrastructure to the SSH, and (3) participated in the workshop DARIAH Aalto Day 2022 at Aalto University.

Internal meetings

KICK-OFF

The FIN-CLARIAH kick-off event took place at the National Library of Finland on 3 June 2022.

During the meeting, all the work packages presented a poster with their work plan.

FIN-CLARIAH DAY

On 18 November 2022, the whole consortium met once again, this time at Jyväskylä University.

The event included a variety of presentations on the state of the project and four thematic groups to develop the steps of DARIAH-FI for 2023 together.

Source: [@kumppis](#)

Roadshows

Since November 2022, part of the DARIAH-FI team has been touring around Finland to introduce the services of the research infrastructure not only to SSH researchers but also to the wider research community.

The first roadshow was held in Tampere University on 10 November 2022. Other roadshows were held in Jyväskylä University on 17 November 2022, University of Eastern Finland on 29 November 2022 and the last one in University of Helsinki on 5 December 2022.

Roadshow participants

180 participants in total

20

Background of the participants

Field of study

- 27 History
 - 15 Linguistics
 - 8 Sociology
 - 7 Social sciences
 - 6 Digital humanities
 - 6 Computer science
 - 3 Education
 - 3 Information studies
 - 3 Applied linguistics
 - 3 Literary studies
 - 3 Linguistic data science
 - 2 Political science
 - 2 English linguistics
 - 2 Data science
 - 2 Criminology
 - 2 Media studies
 - 2 Speech and language technology
 - 2 English language
 - 2 Translation studies
 - 2 Archaeology
 - 2 Corpus linguistics
 - 2 Multimodality research
 - 2 Cultural studies
 - 2 Social psychology
- 67 participants representing individual fields of study

Data from 3 participants missing

Academic background

53 Postgraduate researcher (väitöskirjatutkija)

44 Postdoctoral researcher (postdoc-tutkija)

33 Professor (professori)

17 Master-level student (maisteriopiskelija)

16 Lecturer (lehtori)

15 Other

Data from 2 participants missing

Other activities

On 30 November 2022, part of the DARIAH-FI team was also present at the DARIAH Aalto Day 2022. Arranged by the Semantic Computing Research Group (SeCo), the event took place at Aalto University, one of the DARIAH-FI consortium partners.

In addition to the presentations on the work done so far regarding the development of Linked Open Data infrastructures, the workshop also discussed the next steps of the DARIAH-FI initiative.

DARIAH-FI

ONLINE PRESENCE

In terms of online presence, the DARIAH-FI initiative has two main promotion channels, which are the official website and a Twitter profile.

The Twitter profile was officially launched on 31 May 2022, while the website was officially launched a few days after that, on 2 June 2022.

Official website

Website address:
<https://www.dariah.fi/>

Languages:
Finnish, English

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The screenshot shows the homepage of the DARIAH-FI website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, ABOUT, LOCAL OFFICES, WORK PACKAGES, BLOG & EVENTS, and CONTACT. The main content area features a large blue wireframe graphic on the left and a text block on the right. The text block includes the title "Network for Data-Intensive Social Science and Humanities Research" and a paragraph describing the organization's mission. Below this, there is a section titled "DARIAH-FI on Twitter" with two recent tweets. The first tweet is from Eero Hyvönen, and the second is from DARIAH-FI itself, mentioning a meeting at UEF.

DARIAH-FI

HOME ABOUT LOCAL OFFICES WORK PACKAGES BLOG & EVENTS CONTACT

Network for Data-Intensive Social Science and Humanities Research

DARIAH-FI builds and shares tools, datasets, workflows and teaching materials for the needs of social sciences and humanities (SSH) in Finland. We are a national network connecting universities, individual research groups and data providers together to facilitate high-quality research, especially in the fields of digital humanities and computational social sciences. DARIAH-FI is the Finnish answer to the great changes in the 21st-century scholarship: mass digitization of primary sources, the explosion of born-digital data, novel computational tools and the prospects of supercomputing encourage us to re-think how we make excellent research in social sciences and humanities. Learn more about us [here](#).

DARIAH-FI on Twitter

DARIAH-FI 2 weeks ago
Eero Hyvönen, aka "Ilmarinen of Finnish"

DARIAH-FI 2 weeks ago
DARIAH-FI is going to UEF, time to meet

Twitter profile

Profile address:
[@DariahFi](https://twitter.com/DariahFi)

The screenshot shows the Twitter profile page for DARIAH-FI. The profile picture is a blue wireframe graphic. The bio reads: "We are a national research infrastructure for data-intensive social sciences and humanities, funded by the Academy of Finland." The page also shows the account was joined in April 2022, and has 24 following and 140 followers. A "Follow" button is visible.

← **DARIAH-FI**
15 Tweets

DARIAH-FI

DARIAH-FI
@DariahFi

We are a national research infrastructure for data-intensive social sciences and humanities, funded by the Academy of Finland.

Joined April 2022

24 Following 140 Followers

Follow

DARIAH-FI

FUTURE OF DARIAH-FI

During 2023 and beyond, the roadmap for DARIAH-FI includes various goals. The main objective is to complete the work that is now under construction and launch the different workflows, datasets and tools developed. In the near future, another goal is to join the DARIAH-EU network. To that end, the consortium will apply for a new period of funding for 2024-2025 to further develop the infrastructure.

DARIAH-FI

CONTACT INFORMATION

The executive board of DARIAH-FI can be reached through the website or through the different local offices.

Our offices are local nodes that offer easy access to the national infrastructure. By contacting them, you can meet the DARIAH-FI local representative, plan future collaborations, or simply ask guidance from a real human being.

DARIAH-FI PI

Mikko Tolonen, University of Helsinki
mikko.tolonen@helsinki.fi

DARIAH-FI NATIONAL COORDINATOR

Risto Turunen, University of Helsinki
risto.turunen@helsinki.fi

@DariahFi

www.dariah.fi

